

The Implicit Function Theorem on Banach Spaces from Carathéodory Differentiation

Andrea Carpignani

Department of Mathematics, The Radcliffe School
Christchurch Grove, Wolverton, Milton Keynes, MK12 5BT, UK

9th June 2026

In classical calculus, given a function f , defined on an open interval with values in \mathbb{R} , in order to define the derivative of f at a point x_0 of its domain, one generally starts by taking the *slope function*,

$$R(x_0, x) = \frac{f(x) - f(x_0)}{x - x_0},$$

which is defined for every number x in the domain of f , except x_0 , and then taking the limit of this quantity as x tends towards x_0 . If this limit exists, and if finite, this limit is by definition the *derivative* of f at x_0 , and the function f is called *differentiable* at x_0 .

In a perfectly equivalent way, the previous definition may be rephrased by saying that the function f is differentiable at x_0 if the slope function $R(x_0, x)$, which as we have said is not defined at x_0 , can be extended by continuity at x_0 . Using an old-fashioned terminology, one could say that f is differentiable at x_0 if $R(x_0, x)$ presents a discontinuity of the ‘third species’ at x_0 .

Following an idea of C. Carathéodory, one could utilise the previous remark and, by rearranging the expression which defined the slope function, say that f is differentiable at x_0 if and only if there exists a real function $R(x_0, x)$, continuous at x_0 , such that

$$f(x) = f(x_0) + R(x_0, x)(x - x_0)$$

for every x in the domain of f .

This idea may be generalised to the case of a map between Banach spaces, to give definitions of differentiable function and of derivative that turn out to be completely equivalent to that of Fréchet derivative, but which has the advantage of being exclusively based on continuity, and which simplifies some of the proofs.

We shall refer to this as *Carathéodory differentiation*, and in the sequel we shall prove the algebraic properties of Carathéodory differentiation, we shall discuss the equivalence with Fréchet differentiation, and we shall derive the implicit function theorem, using general arguments of functional analysis largely based on the algebraic and topological nature of Banach spaces.

1. Carathéodory differentiation

Let us recall that a Banach space E is a vector space on the field of real numbers endowed with a norm, which we are going to denote by $\|\cdot\|_E$, which makes it a complete space. If E and F are two Banach spaces, we shall denote by $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$ the algebra of all bounded linear operators from E to F . Let us recall that this is itself a Banach space with the norm defined by

$$\|T\|_{\mathcal{L}(E, F)} = \sup_{x \neq 0} \frac{\|T(x)\|_F}{\|x\|_E} = \sup_{\|x\|_E=1} \|T(x)\|_F = \sup_{\|x\|_E \leq 1} \|T(x)\|_F.$$

We shall also denote by $\text{GL}(E)$ the open subset of $\mathcal{L}(E, E)$ of all invertible bounded linear operators on E . The space $\mathcal{L}(E, \mathbb{R})$ shall be denoted by E^* and is called the (*topological*) *dual* of E . If ω is an element of E^* and x is an element of E , instead of $\omega(x)$ we shall preferably write $\langle \omega, x \rangle$ to emphasise the dual nature between E and E^* .

(1.1) Definition. Let E and F be two Banach spaces, let U be an open subset of E , x_0 a point in U , and f be a function defined on U with values in F . We shall say that f is (*Carathéodory*) *differentiable* at x_0 if there exists a function L_{x_0} , defined on U , with values in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$, continuous at x_0 , called a *slope function* at x_0 , such that

$$(1.2) \quad f(x) = f(x_0) + L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0)$$

for every point x in U .

(1.3) Remark. In the same hypotheses of Definition (1.1), observe that a slope function need not be unique. Indeed, if x_0 and x are two points in U , observe that rearranging (1.2) gives

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0),$$

and, for every linear operator $T_{x_0}(x)$ in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$ such that $T_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0) = 0$, the function $L_{x_0}^*(x) = L_{x_0}(x) + T_{x_0}(x)$ is also a slope function.

Even though the slope function is not uniquely determined, however, the value at the point x_0 is. In fact, from (1.2), if u is an element of E and t a real number such that $x_0 + tu$ belongs to U , one has

$$L_{x_0}(x_0 + tu)u = \frac{f(x_0 + tu) - f(x_0)}{t}$$

and taking the limit as $t \rightarrow 0$, the left-hand side of the previous equation tends to $L_{x_0}(x_0)u$ because L_{x_0} is by definition continuous at x_0 , and the right-hand side does not depend on the function L_{x_0} .

(1.4) Remark. Still in the same the hypotheses of Definition (1.1), observe that if f is differentiable at x_0 , then it is also continuous at x_0 . In fact, from (1.2), it

follows that

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = L_{x_0}(x_0)(x - x_0)$$

and the continuity of f at x_0 follows from the fact that, by hypothesis, L_{x_0} is continuous at x_0 and that $L_{x_0}(x)$ is a continuous linear operator from E to F .

(1.5) Definition. Let E and F be two Banach spaces, let U be an open subset of E , x_0 a point in U , f be a function from E to F , differentiable at x_0 , and L_{x_0} a slope function of f at x_0 . Then, the linear operator $L_{x_0}(x_0)$ in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$ (which is unique by virtue of Remark (1.3)) is called the *derivative* of f at x_0 , and shall be denoted by $Df(x_0)$.

2. Equivalence with Fréchet differentiation

(2.1) Definition. Let E and F be two Banach spaces, U a non-empty open subset of E , x_0 an element of U and f a function from U to F . We shall say that f is *Fréchet differentiable* at x_0 if there exists a linear operator $A(x_0)$ in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$ such that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \frac{\|f(x) - f(x_0) - A(x_0)(x - x_0)\|_F}{\|x - x_0\|_E} = 0.$$

(2.2) Proposition. A function f is Carathéodory differentiable at x_0 if and only if it is Fréchet differentiable at x_0 .

Proof. Let us start by assuming that f is Carathéodory differentiable at x_0 , and let L_{x_0} be a slope function. Let us also set $A(x_0) = Df(x_0) = L_{x_0}(x_0)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\|f(x) - f(x_0) - A(x_0)(x - x_0)\|_F}{\|x - x_0\|_E} &= \frac{\|L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0) - Df(x_0)(x - x_0)\|_F}{\|x - x_0\|_E} \\ &\leq \frac{\|L_{x_0}(x) - L_{x_0}(x_0)\|_{\mathcal{L}(E, F)} \cdot \|x - x_0\|_E}{\|x - x_0\|_E} \\ &= \|L_{x_0}(x) - L_{x_0}(x_0)\|_{\mathcal{L}(E, F)} \end{aligned}$$

and the right-hand side tends towards 0 because L_{x_0} is continuous at x_0 .

Conversely, let us assume that f is Fréchet differentiable at x_0 , and let $A(x_0)$ be a linear operator in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$ such that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \frac{\|f(x) - f(x_0) - A(x_0)(x - x_0)\|_F}{\|x - x_0\|_E} = 0.$$

Let x be a point in U , and with the aid of Hahn-Banach Theorem, we may consider a linear functional $\omega(x_0, x)$ in E^* such that

$$\langle \omega(x_0, x), x - x_0 \rangle = 1,$$

and E may be written as the direct sum $\langle x - x_0 \rangle \oplus \ker \omega(x_0, x)$. It suffices to define $L_{x_0}(x)$ on $x - x_0$ and $\ker \omega(x_0, x)$ separately. Let us take, for every real number t and every element u of $\ker \omega(x_0, x)$,

$$L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0) = f(x) - f(x_0), \quad L_{x_0}u = A(x_0)u.$$

Then, if $\xi \in E$, one has $\xi = t(x - x_0) + u$ for some real number t and some element u of $\ker \omega(x_0, x)$, whence

$$\begin{aligned} L_{x_0}(x)\xi &= t[f(x) - f(x_0)] + A(x_0)u \\ &= [f(x) - f(x_0) - A(x_0)(x - x_0)] \langle \omega(x_0, x), \xi \rangle + A(x_0)\xi, \end{aligned}$$

and this function is continuous at x_0 and satisfies $f(x) - f(x_0) = L_{x_0}(x - x_0)$, hence it is a slope function for f at x_0 , and this proves that f is Carathéodory differentiable at x_0 . \square

3. Rules of differentiation

(3.1) Proposition (Linearity). *Let f and g be two functions defined on two possibly different domains, but both containing a non-empty open subset U of E , with values in F . Let x_0 be a point in U , and let a and b be two real numbers. If f and g are both differentiable at x_0 , then the function $af + bg$ is differentiable at x_0 , and*

$$D(af + bg)(x_0) = aDf(x_0) + bDg(x_0).$$

Proof. By hypotheses, there exist two maps L_{x_0} and M_{x_0} , defined on U , with values in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$, such that

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0), \quad g(x) - g(x_0) = M_{x_0}(x - x_0)$$

for every x in U . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (af + bg)(x) - (af + bg)(x_0) &= af(x) + bg(x) - af(x_0) - bg(x_0) \\ &= a(f(x) - f(x_0)) + b(g(x) - g(x_0)) \\ &= aL_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0) + bM_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0) \\ &= (aL_{x_0}(x) + bM_{x_0}(x))(x - x_0) \end{aligned}$$

and the conclusion follows observing that the map $aL_{x_0} + bM_{x_0}$ is continuous at x_0 , hence a slope function for $af + bg$ at x_0 . \square

(3.2) Proposition (Chain rule). *Let E, F and G be three Banach spaces, let f be a function from a non-empty open subset U of E to F , let g be a function from a non-empty open subset V of F to G , and assume that $f(U) \subseteq V$. Let x_0 be a point in U . If the functions f and g are differentiable at x_0 and $f(x_0)$, respectively, then the composite function $g \circ f$ is differentiable at x_0 , and*

$$D(g \circ f)(x_0) = Dg(f(x_0))Df(x_0).$$

Proof. By hypotheses, there exist two maps L_{x_0} , from U to $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$, and $M_{f(x_0)}$, from V to $\mathcal{L}(F, G)$, such that

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0), \quad g(y) - g(f(x_0)) = M_{f(x_0)}(y)(y - f(x_0))$$

for every x in U and y in V . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (g \circ f)(x) - (g \circ f)(x_0) &= g(f(x)) - g(f(x_0)) \\ &= M_{f(x_0)}(f(x))(f(x) - f(x_0)) \\ &= M_{f(x_0)}(f(x))L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0) \end{aligned}$$

and the conclusion follows observing that the map $M_{f(x_0)}(f(x))L_{x_0}(x)$ is continuous at x_0 , hence it is a slope function for $g \circ f$ at x_0 . \square

In a Banach space, generally, a product may not be defined. On the other hand, from an algebraic point of view, a product is just a symmetric bilinear form. Thus, a generalisation of Leibniz formula for the product of two function may be given in terms of a symmetric bilinear map. To this end, it shall be useful to introduce some notation.

If \mathfrak{b} is a symmetric bilinear form defined on F with values in G , and if f, g are two functions defined in two possibly different domains of E , containing a common non-empty open subset U with values in F , we shall denote by $\mathfrak{b}(f, g)$ the function, defined on U with values in G by

$$x \mapsto \mathfrak{b}(f(x), g(x)).$$

In addition, if T is a linear operator from E to F , and y is an element of F , we shall denote by $\mathfrak{b}(T, y)$ the map defined on E by

$$x \mapsto \mathfrak{b}(Tx, y).$$

With these notations in mind, we can now prove the following.

(3.3) Proposition (Leibniz formula). *Let f and g be two functions defined on two possibly different domains, but both containing a non-empty open set U of a Banach space E , with values in a Banach space F . Let \mathfrak{b} be a symmetric bilinear function on F with values in another Banach space G , and let x_0 be a point in U . If f and g are both differentiable at x_0 , then the function $\mathfrak{b}(f, g)$ is differentiable at x_0 , and*

$$D(\mathfrak{b}(f, g))(x_0) = \mathfrak{b}(Df(x_0), g(x_0)) + \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), Dg(x_0)).$$

Proof. Let us set $h(x) = \mathfrak{b}(f(x), g(x))$. By hypotheses, there exist two maps L_{x_0} and M_{x_0} , defined on U , with values in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$, such that

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0), \quad g(x) - g(x_0) = M_{x_0}(x - x_0)$$

for every x in U . Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
h(x) - h(x_0) &= \mathfrak{b}(f(x), g(x)) - \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), g(x)) + \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), g(x)) - \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), g(x_0)) \\
&= \mathfrak{b}(f(x) - f(x_0), g(x)) + \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), g(x) - g(x_0)) \\
&= \mathfrak{b}(L_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0), g(x)) + \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), M_{x_0}(x)(x - x_0)) \\
&= [\mathfrak{b}(L_{x_0}(x), g(x)) + \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), M_{x_0}(x))] (x - x_0)
\end{aligned}$$

and the conclusion follows from the fact that $\mathfrak{b}(L_{x_0}(x), g(x)) + \mathfrak{b}(f(x_0), M_{x_0}(x))$ is continuous at x_0 because composition of continuous functions at x_0 , hence it is a slope function for $h = \mathfrak{b}(f, g)$ at x_0 . \square

4. Differentiable functions on a product space

(4.1) Remark. Let E_1 , E_2 and F be three Banach spaces, and let T be a linear operator from $E_1 \times E_2$ to F , that is to say an element of $\mathcal{L}(E_1 \times E_2, F)$. Then, we can always find two linear operators α and β , in $\mathcal{L}(E_1, F)$ and $\mathcal{L}(E_2, F)$, respectively, such that

$$T(x) = \alpha(x_1) + \beta(x_2) \quad \text{for every } x = (x_1, x_2) \in E_1 \times E_2.$$

In order to see this, it suffices define

$$\alpha(x_1) = T(x_1, 0), \quad \beta(x_2) = T(0, x_2)$$

and to use the decomposition $x = (x_1, x_2) = (x_1, 0) + (0, x_2)$ and the linearity of T to separate the two functions.

(4.2) Definition. Let E_1 , E_2 and F be three Banach spaces, Ω a non-empty open subset of $E_1 \times E_2$, $x_0 = (x_{01}, x_{02})$ an element of Ω , and f a function defined on Ω , with values in F , differentiable at x_0 . By the previous remark, any slope function L_{x_0} of f at x_0 can be written in the form

$$L_{x_0}(u) = \alpha_{x_0}(u_1) + \beta_{x_0}(u_2) \quad \text{for every } u = (u_1, u_2) \in E_1 \times E_2.$$

Then, the two linear operators $\alpha_{x_0}(x_{01})$ and $\beta_{x_0}(x_{02})$ shall be called the **partial derivative** of f at x_0 , and shall be denoted by

$$D_{x_1}f(x_0) \quad \text{and} \quad D_{x_2}f(x_0),$$

respectively.

5. Continuously differentiable functions

(5.1) Definition. Let E and F be two Banach spaces, let U be an open subset of E , and f be a function defined on U with values in F . We shall say that f is differentiable **on** U if f is differentiable at every point x in U .

(5.2) Remark. In the hypotheses of the previous definition, let us observe immediately that, if a function f defined on subset U of a Banach space E , with values in a Banach space F , is differentiable on U , then, for every x in U there exists a slope function L_x , continuous at x . Thus, we can consider the function L , defined on $U \times U$, with values in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$, by

$$(x, x') \mapsto L(x, x') = L_x(x').$$

This function may be referred to as the **slope function** of f on U . Observe that this function need not be continuous, but the only requirement is that for every point x in U , the function $x' \mapsto L(x, x')$ is continuous at x .

From the previous remark, it follows that, in general, if f is differentiable on U , the function $x \mapsto Df(x)$, that to each element x of U associates the derivative of f at x , need not be continuous, nor is it expected to be such. On the other hand, any meaningful result will require some properties of continuity for this function. For this reason, let us give the following definition.

(5.3) Definition. Let E and F be two Banach spaces, let U be an open subset of E , x_0 a point in U , and f be a function from U to F , differentiable on U . We shall say that f is **continuously differentiable** at x_0 if the function $x \mapsto Df(x)$, from U to $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$, called the **derivative** of f , is continuous at x_0 .

Furthermore, if f is continuously differentiable at every point x in U , we shall say that f is continuously differentiable **on** U .

(5.4) Lemma. Let E and F be two Banach spaces, let U be a non-empty open subset of E , x_0 a point in U , and f a function from U to F , differentiable on U . If f is continuously differentiable at x_0 , then we can find a slope function L^* such that $(x, y) \mapsto L^*(x, y)$ is continuous at (x_0, x_0) .

Proof. By hypothesis, there exists a slope function L , defined on $U \times U$, with values in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$ such that

$$f(x') = f(x) + L(x, x')(x - x')$$

for every pair x, x' of elements of U .

Since, by hypothesis, the function $x \mapsto L(x, x)$ is continuous at x_0 , for every strictly positive real number ε , there exists an open neighbourhood U_ε of x_0 in U such that, for every x in U_ε , one has

$$\|Df(x) - Df(x_0)\|_{\mathcal{L}(E, F)} < \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon.$$

With no loss of generality, we can also assume that U_ε is convex, because the open balls, which are convex, form a system of generators for the topology in E .

Now, let us pick two distinct points x and x' in U_ε , and observe that, by virtue of Hahn-Banach Theorem, there exists a linear functional $\omega(x, x')$ on the dual E^* of E , such that

$$\langle \omega(x, x'), x' - x \rangle = 1,$$

and the space E may be decomposed into the direct sum $\langle x' - x \rangle \oplus \ker \omega(x, x')$. It suffices to define a new slope function on $x' - x$ and on $\ker \omega(x, x')$ separately. Let us set

$$L^*(x', x)(x' - x) = L(x', x)(x' - x) = f(x') - f(x)$$

and for every u in $\ker \omega(x, x')$, set

$$L^*(x', x)u = Df(x)u.$$

Then, L^* is a function on $U \times U$ with values in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$, the function $x' \mapsto L^*(x, x')$ is continuous at x , and therefore it is a slope. It suffices to prove that L^* is continuous at (x_0, x_0) . In other words, we wish to prove that, for every x, x' in U_ε , we have

$$\|L^*(x, x') - Df(x_0)\|_{\mathcal{L}(E, F)} < \varepsilon.$$

Taking an element ξ in E , thanks to the decomposition $E = \langle x' - x \rangle \oplus \ker \omega(x', x)$, there exist a real number t , that with no loss of generality may be taken smaller than 1, and an element u in $\ker \omega(x', x)$ such that

$$\xi = t(x' - x) + u, \quad \|L^*(x, x')\xi - Df(x_0)\xi\|_F \leq A + B,$$

$$A = \|L^*(x, x')(x' - x) - Df(x)(x' - x)\|_F, \quad B = \|L^*(x, x')u - Df(x)u\|_F.$$

Let us estimate A and B separately. The second one is simpler. Since u is an element of $\ker \omega(x, x')$, by definition of L^* , one has

$$B = \|L^*(x, x')u - Df(x)u\|_F = \|Df(x)u - Df(x_0)u\|_F < \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon,$$

because x and x' are by hypothesis in U_ε .

The first term is slightly more tedious. Let us start by observing that, thanks to Hahn-Banach Theorem, there exists in F^* a linear functional λ , with $\|\lambda\|_{F^*} = 1$, such that

$$\langle \lambda, L(x, x')(x' - x) - Df(x_0)(x' - x) \rangle = A,$$

Let us consider the real function ψ , defined on $[0, 1]$ by

$$\psi(r) = \langle \lambda, f(x + r(x' - x)) - f(x) - rDf(x_0)(x' - x) \rangle.$$

Clearly, one has $\psi(0) = 0$, $\psi(1) = A$ and thanks to the fact that f is differentiable on U , ψ is differentiable and

$$\psi'(r) = \langle \lambda, Df(x + r(x' - x))(x' - x) - Df(x_0)(x' - x) \rangle.$$

By virtue of the Mean Value Theorem, there exists a real number r_0 in $(0, 1)$, such that

$$A = \psi(1) - \psi(0) = \psi'(r_0),$$

that is to say

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \langle \lambda, Df(x + r_0(x' - x))(x' - x) - Df(x_0)(x' - x) \rangle \\ &\leq \|Df(x + r_0(x' - x))(x' - x) - Df(x_0)(x' - x)\|_F \leq \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

because x and x' are by hypothesis in U_ε and also $x + r_0(x' - x) \in U_\varepsilon$, because the neighbourhood U_ε has been assumed to be convex. Thus, in the end,

$$\|L^*(x, x')\xi - Df(x_0)\xi\|_F \leq A + B < \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon = \varepsilon,$$

and this proves that $(x, x') \mapsto L^*(x, x')$ is continuous at (x_0, x_0) . \square

6. The implicit function theorem

We have now all necessary tools to prove the implicit function theorem.

(6.1) Theorem (Implicit Function Theorem). *Let E and F be two Banach spaces, let Ω be a subset of $E \times F$, and f a function defined on Ω with values in F , continuously differentiable on Ω . Suppose there exists a point (x_0, y_0) in Ω such that*

$$f(x_0, y_0) = 0, \quad D_y f(x_0, y_0) \in \text{GL}(F).$$

Then, there exists a neighbourhood U of x_0 and a neighbourhood V of y_0 , such that $U \times V \subseteq \Omega$, and a function φ , from U to V , such that

$$f(x, \varphi(x)) = 0 \quad \text{for every } x \text{ in } U.$$

Furthermore, the function φ is continuously differentiable on U and

$$D\varphi(x) = -D_y f(x, \varphi(x))^{-1} D_x f(x, \varphi(x)) \quad \text{for every } x \text{ in } U.$$

Proof. Since the function f is by hypothesis continuously differentiable on Ω , by virtue of Lemma (5.4), there exists a slope function L , defined on $\Omega \times \Omega$, with values in $\mathcal{L}(E \times F, F)$ which is continuous at (x_0, x_0) . Such a slope function can also be written, by virtue of Remark (4.1) that

$$L(x, x')(u, v) = \alpha(x, x')u + \beta(x, x')v \quad \text{for every } u \in E \text{ and } v \in F,$$

where α and β are two functions defined on $\Omega \times \Omega$, with values in $\mathcal{L}(E, F)$ and $\mathcal{L}(F, F)$, respectively, continuous at x_0 and y_0 respectively, and such that

$$\beta(x_0, y_0, x_0, y_0) = D_y f(x_0, y_0) \in \text{GL}(F).$$

Since the latter is an open subset of $\mathcal{L}(F, F)$, there exists an open neighbourhood of (x_0, y_0) in Ω , which can be taken of the form $U \times V$, where U is an open neighbourhood of x_0 , and V is open neighbourhood of y_0 , such that

$$\beta(x_0, y_0, x, y) \in \text{GL}(F) \quad \text{for every } x \in U \text{ and } y \in V.$$

Let $x \in U$, $y, y' \in V$ such that $f(x, y) = f(x, y') = 0$, and observe that

$$\beta(x, y, x, y')(y' - y) = L(x, y, x, y')(x - x, y' - y) = f(x, y') - f(x, y) = 0$$

and since $\beta(x, y, x, y)$ is invertible by assumption, it follows that $y' - y = 0$, which entails $y' = y$. This shows that the set

$$\{(x, y) \in U \times V : f(x, y) = 0\}$$

is a functional relation in $U \times V$, whence it defines a function from U to V . Let us denote by φ the function defined by this relation. It only remains to prove that φ is continuously differentiable on U . To this end, observe that, if x and x' are two points in U , then $f(x', \varphi(x')) = f(x, \varphi(x)) = 0$, and, setting

$$\alpha(x, x') = \alpha(x, \varphi(x), x', \varphi(x')), \quad \beta(x, x') = \beta(x, \varphi(x), x', \varphi(x')),$$

one has

$$0 = f(x', \varphi(x')) - f(x, \varphi(x)) = \alpha(x, x')(x' - x) + \beta(x, x')(\varphi(x') - \varphi(x))$$

and since $\beta \in \text{GL}(F)$, one finally gets

$$\varphi(x') - \varphi(x) = (-\beta(x, x')^{-1}\alpha(x, x'))(x' - x).$$

Finally, setting $T(x, x') = -\beta(x, x')^{-1}\alpha(x, x')$, it is clear that $(x, x') \mapsto T(x, x')$ is a slope function for φ , and

$$D\varphi(x) = T(x, x) = -\beta(x, x)^{-1}\alpha(x, x) = -D_y f(x, \varphi(x))^{-1} D_x f(x, \varphi(x))$$

and the theorem is completely proved. \square

A. Hahn-Banach theorem and consequences

Throughout the paper, we have summoned a few times Hahn-Banach Theorem as an aid to construct a linear functional with a certain value on a given point. The purpose of this appendix is to briefly recall the statement of this classical theorem in linear functional analysis, and to show explicitly how this can be used to construct a bounded linear functional with a specific value on a given vector, or with a specific norm.

(A.1) Theorem (Hahn-Banach). *Let E be a real normed space, and let p be a positively homogeneous and sub-additive functional defined on E . Let E_0 be a proper subspace of E , and λ a linear functional defined on E_0 such that*

$$\langle \lambda, x \rangle \leq p(x) \quad \text{for every } x \text{ in } E_0.$$

Then there exists at least one linear functional Λ on E , whose restriction to E_0 coincides with λ , and such that

$$\langle \Lambda, x \rangle \leq p(x) \quad \text{for every } x \text{ in } E_0.$$

Let us now suppose that E is a Banach space, and let u be an element of E , with $u \neq 0$. Our first objective is to construct a continuous linear functional Λ on E , such that $\langle \Lambda, u \rangle = 1$. To this end, let us consider the subspace

$$E_0 = \langle u \rangle = \{tu : t \in \mathbb{R}\}$$

and we can easily construct a linear functional λ on E_0 by setting

$$\langle \lambda, tu \rangle = t \quad \text{for every } t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

In order to apply Hahn-Banach Theorem, let us take $p(x) = \|u\|_E^{-1} \|x\|_E$. This is clearly a positively homogeneous sub-linear functional on E , and by construction, one also has

$$\langle \lambda, tu \rangle = t = p(tu) \quad \text{for every } t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Thus, by virtue of Hahn-Banach theorem, there exists a linear functional Λ on E which extends λ , and such that

$$\langle \Lambda, x \rangle \leq \frac{\|x\|_E}{\|u\|_E} \quad \text{for every } x \in E.$$

Observe that, thanks to the previous condition, $\|\Lambda\|_{E^*} = \|u\|_E^{-1}$, hence Λ is also continuous, hence an element of E^* .

Now, to construct a functional whose norm is 1, in lieu of $\langle \lambda, tu \rangle = t$, it suffices to take the linear functional on E_0 defined by

$$\langle \lambda, tu \rangle = t\|u\|_E \quad \text{for every } t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Using the same positively homogeneous sub-linear functional $p(x) = \|u\|_E^{-1} \|x\|_E$, thanks to Hahn-Banach Theorem there exists now a continuous linear functional Λ on E such that $\langle \Lambda, u \rangle = \|u\|_E$ and $\|\Lambda\|_{E^*} = 1$.

References

- [1] P. Acquistapace. *Lecture Notes on Functional Analysis*. Chapman-Hall (2026)
- [2] E. Acosta, C. Delgado. “Fréchet vs. Carathéodory”. *Amer. Math. Monthly* 101 (1994), 332–338
- [3] S. Arora, H. Browne, D. Daners. “An alternative approach to Fréchet derivatives”. *Journal of the Australian Mathematical Society*. 111(2) (2021) 202–220
- [4] C. Carathéodory. *Funktionentheorie. Band I*. Birkhäuser (1950) (German)